

Structural Studies of n-CdO with p-PEDOT: PSS Heterojunction Films

Synthesized by Low-cost Method

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Abstract

The commercially available poly (3, 4 ethylenedioxytheophene: poly (styrene sulfonic acid)) (PEDOT:PSS) was deposited by using dip coating technique onto n-CdO necklace type nanostructures synthesized by simple chemical route to get high surface area heterojunction network. The structural properties of the films were measured by using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) technique whereas surface morphology was viewed by high resolution Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, JEOL 6360A), attached with energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDAX). The surface morphology of necklace like nanostructure CdO film under different magnifications

Keywords: n-CdO/p-PEDOT:PSS; chemical route; nanoheterojunction.

1. Introduction

A nanostructure such as nanowires, nanotubes, nanorods etc. has an importance in basic the scientific research and its potential in technological applications. Wide efforts have been taken for the synthesis of the semiconducting nanomaterial with different nanoforms such as nanorods [1-3], nanowires [4] and nanotubes [5] etc. The nanoheterojunction can be synthesized by the deposition of p-type semiconducting inorganic or organic material on n-type semiconducting material synthesized in the form of nanowires or nanotubes or nanorods etc. In recent years, the conducting polymers have been widely investigated as effective materials for room temperature chemical sensors. PEDOT:PSS is commonly accepted to be more environmentally stable than other conducting polymers such as polypyrrole and polyaniline. These features make PEDOT:PSS and its derivatives appealing for gas sensing applications [6]. The Cadmium oxide (CdO), a II-VI group, is an important n-type semiconducting material with direct band gap of 2.5 eV and indirect band gap 1.98 eV [7]. CdO is most promising semiconducting material for different applications such as in solar cells, phototransistors, catalysts and gas sensors [8].

In the present investigation, effort has been taken for the synthesis of necklace like nanostructure of inorganic n-type semiconducting material CdO and formation of a nanoheterojunction by deposition of organic p-PEDOT: PSS on n-CdO. The very low cost and room temperature chemical route was used for the synthesis of the nanoheterojunction films on fluorine doped tin oxide (FTO) coated glass substrates. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectrum of CdO nanonecklace and CdO/PEDOT: PSS on FTO is investigated. The intensity of generated X-ray is related to the concentration fraction of each element present in the target material. Comparing elemental spectrum of bare CdO with PEDOT: PSS coated CdO nanonecklace, existence of Cd and O peak are observed which confirms the formation CdO.

The carbon content in the PEDOT: PSS coated CdO nanostructure gives rough confirmation towards the existence of PEDOT: PSS layer on CdO.

2. Experimental details

2.1 Synthesis of CdO necklace type nanostructure

Initially, Cd(OH)₂ nanowires were synthesized at room temperature by using chemical method reported earlier [9]. Specifically, 0.1 M/L (50 mL) CdCl₂ was complexed by drop wise addition of ammonia (10 mL) to the solution. The pH of the complexed bath was maintained at 12. The solution was stirred for few seconds and gently immersed the well cleaned FTO coated glass substrates vertically in a solution along the wall of the beaker at room temperature [27 °C]. After 21 h, the white Cd(OH)₂ film was deposited on the substrate surface. Then, substrate was taken out from the solution, rinsed with double distilled water and dried in dry air [10]. CdO necklace like nanostructure film was obtained by annealing Cd(OH)₂ film at optimized temperature of 290 °C in contact with air for two hours.

2.2 Deposition PEDOT:PSS on CdO necklace type nanostructure

The deposition of PEDOT: PSS on CdO nanostructure was performed by using simple dipping technique. Commercially available PEDOT: PSS solution from Baytron (HC Starck's Clevios PH1000) was used to form the shell. Different ratios of PEDOT: PSS::H₂O was used and the ratio 1:4 was found to be optimal. For this, PEDOT: PSS containing 80% water was coated on FTO/CdO film by using dip coating technique. At each time, each volume of PEDOT: PSS::H₂O was ultrasonicated for 1 h. For single dip, FTO/CdO film was dipped vertically into PEDOT: PSS: H₂O solution for 2-3 seconds and taken out vertically. After 4 to 5 such a dips in the intervals of few seconds, a very thin, homogeneous layer of PEDOT: PSS was coated on CdO. The dip coated film of FTO/CdO/PEDOT:PSS was heated at 100 °C for 10 min in air. The PEDOT: PSS::H₂O ratio, ultrasonication, dipping and heating times were

optimized with respect to get uniform and thin layer coating of PEDOT: PSS on CdO necklace type nanostructure towards better gas sensing performance.

2.3 Characterizations

The structural properties of the films were measured by using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) technique where as surface morphology was viewed by high resolution Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, JEOL 6360A), attached with energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDAX). The gas sensing properties of n-CdO/p-PEDOT:PSS were studied on the home made gas sensor unit, under forward biased current density–voltage (J–V) characteristics between 0 and 2 V.

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Surface morphological studies and elemental analysis

The surface morphology of necklace like nanostructure CdO film under different magnifications are as shown fig.1 (a) and (b) for 1 μm and 500 nm respectively whereas fig 1 (c) and (d) for PEDOT:PSS coated CdO necklace like nanostructure with magnifications of 1 μm and 500 nm, respectively. From fig.1(a), it clearly shows the string of small beads to form necklace like nanostructures. With higher magnification (500 nm), the random distribution of CdO nanonecklace spread on FTO substrate with enough porous surface area is observed (fig.1 (b)). It is quite difficult to observe coating of PEDOT:PSS on CdO, rather blurred image gives prediction about the coating of polymer. The lower magnification image clearly depicts the formation of blurred CdO necklace like nanostructure confirming uniform coating of PEDOT: PSS over the CdO necklace nanostructure (fig.1(c)). At higher magnification, it is observed that PEDOT: PSS slurry was uniformly coated on CdO to form nanoheterojunction (fig.1 (d)).

At the junction between necklaces, PEDOT:PSS stacked to form the bigger particles due to agglomeration of PEDOT:PSS which clearly visualized in lower as well as higher magnification images. The uniform growth of p-type polymer on the n-type necklace nanostructure results into the formation of high surface area p–n junction at the nano level and hence, the formation of nanoheterojunction.

Figure 1. Field Effect Scanning Electron Microscopic Images of CdO and CdO + PEDOT: PSS thin films a) CdO thin film with 1µm scale b) CdO thin films with 500 nm scale, c) CdO + PEDOT: PSS thin film with 1µm scale, and d) CdO + PEDOT: PSS thin film with 500 nm scale,

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectrum of CdO nanonecklace and CdO/PEDOT: PSS on FTO is as shown in fig.2. The intensity of generated X-ray is related to the concentration fraction of each element present in the target material. Comparing elemental spectrum of bare CdO (fig.2 (a)) with PEDOT: PSS coated CdO nanonecklace (fig.2 (b)), existence of Cd and

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O peak are observed which confirms the formation CdO. The carbon content in the PEDOT: PSS coated CdO nanostructure gives rough confirmation towards the existence of PEDOT: PSS layer on CdO. The appearance of Sn in CdO is contribution from FTO coated glass substrate. The intensity of Sn peak diminished in PEDOT: PSS coated CdO nanostructure, which shows coating of polymer layer on CdO.

Figure 2: Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectrum of a) bare CdO and b) with PEDOT: PSS coated CdO nanonecklace thin films.

3.2 Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) studies of CdO and PEDOT:PSS deposited CdO

Fig.3 (a) shows the FT-IR spectrum of CdO necklace type nanostructure. The peak at 1437 cm^{-1} attributed to C-C stretching of aromatics. The peaks at 854 cm^{-1} and 640 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C-Cl and C-Br stretching of alkyl halides respectively. Inclusion of Cl-group is from used cadmium chloride as a source material. The FT-IR spectrum of PEDOT: PSS coated on CdO nanostructure is as shown in fig.3 (b). The aromatic band due to extended resonance the of polar characteristic related C=C double bond stretching at about 1641.28 cm^{-1} in five member vinyl ether group assigned to thiophene ring. The band at 1199 cm^{-1} occurs

due to the C-O stretching. The small peak at 1043 cm^{-1} may be due to symmetric stretching of S=O [11, 12].

Fig.3. FT-IR absorption spectrum of (a) CdO and (b) PEDOT:PSS coated CdO

4. Conclusions

In present work, we have successfully synthesized necklace like nanostructure of n-CdO onto FTO coated glass substrates by simple and low cost chemical method followed by deposition of p-PEDOT:PSS on n-CdO by simple dipping technique. Formation of such a novel

morphology of n-CdO/p-PEDOT:PSS necklace type nanoheterojunction with high surface area leads to demonstrate a gas sensors and phototransistors.

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